

Three main structures of behavior economy in the US: political party behavior economy, politician behavior economy and government behavior economy

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Abstract

This article provides an in-depth analysis of the phenomena of party behavior economy, politician behavior economy and government behavior economy in the US economy. The economic decisions made by the US government under the leadership of Joe Biden have become research samples, covering aspects such as economic growth rate, US dollar monetary policy, the situation of US Treasury bonds, inflation, employment situation, and economic policies towards China and Europe. Although economic policies of the Biden administration are intended to stimulate economic growth, their actual effects are restricted by various factors. In terms of monetary policy, the interest rate hikes of the Federal Reserve have brought about a chain reaction; the continuous increase in the scale of US Treasury bonds has raised concerns about the sustainability of US debt; the problem of inflation is prominent, and the effect of governance is not satisfactory; the recovery of the employment market is facing numerous difficulties. In terms of foreign economic policies, the policy of economic containment against China has continued, and policies towards Europe are complex and there are frictions.

The performance of the U.S. national economy is highly correlated with the behavior of political parties, politicians and government. Different political party ideologies lead to differences in economic policies. For example, the Democratic Party tends to advocate government intervention, while the Republican Party emphasizes the free market. Decisions made by politicians also affect economic trends, as their political stances and the influence of interest groups can sway the formulation of economic policies.

The economic and political systems in the US were established and evolved under the dominance of politicians and political parties. There are significant differences in the systems of different partisan governments, which have a profound impact on the economy. The institutional economy in the US is the product of politician behavior economy and party behavior economy. Without considering political factors, it is impossible to fully understand the institutional economy.

The behaviors of politicians, political parties, politics and government are the origin of institutional economics, and the development of institutional economics is also inseparable from the understanding of politician behavior economy, party behavior economy, political behavior economy and government behavior economy. Establishing new disciplines of party behavior economics, politician behavior economics, political behavior economics and government behavioral economics is of

great value in analyzing the rise and fall of a country's economy, including gaining an in-depth understanding of the origin of economic policies, revealing the political factors in economic development, and optimizing the design of economic institutions. It is also of value in analyzing the rise and fall of the world economy, such as interpreting the political motives in international economic relations, predicting the trend of global economic policies, and promoting international economic cooperation and coordination. However, the study of the top level of institutional economics also needs to be based on the reclassification of human social systems.

Keywords: political party behavior economy · politician behavior economy · government behavioral economy · political behavior economy · political party behavior economics · politician or statesman behavior economics · government behavior economics · political behavior economics · institutional economics

1. Introduction

The U.S. economy plays an important role in the global economic landscape. The direction of its economic policies and behavior not only affects the rise and fall of its own economy, but also has a profound ripple effect on the world economy. The many decisions of the U.S. government under the leadership of Biden have become typical samples for observing U.S. economic behavior. Behind these behaviors, the factors of politics, political parties and politicians are always present, highlighting the key role of political party behavior economy, politician behavior economy and government behavioral economy. An in-depth analysis of this phenomenon is indispensable value for understanding the operating mechanism of the U.S. economy and the dynamic changes in the global economy.

2. The Impact of Biden's Political Parties and Government on the U.S. Economy

2.1. Economic growth rate

After taking office, the Biden administration implemented a series of economic policies with the intention of stimulating economic growth. For example, large-scale infrastructure bills and budget resolutions were passed during his tenure. Taking the \$550 billion infrastructure bill as an example, it is invested in fields such as transportation infrastructure, electric vehicles, water and electricity. In theory, it can drive the development of related industries. For example, capital investment in repairing roads and bridges will promote business growth in industries such as construction and materials, and then drive economic growth. However, the actual effects of these policies are restricted by multiple factors. On the one hand, there are delays and inadequate implementation in the process of policy implementation. For example, infrastructure projects may progress slowly due to cumbersome procedures such as land approval and environmental assessment. On the other hand, uncertainties in the external environment, such as global economic fluctuations and trade tensions, also interfere with economic growth. Judging from the data, the U.S. economic growth rate has fluctuated to a certain extent during Biden's tenure. Although the economy has grown in some periods, due to factors such as inflation and

debt, the sustainability of economic growth faces challenges.

2.2. U.S. dollar monetary policy

U.S. dollar monetary policy is an important means of economic regulation in the United States. During the Biden administration, the Federal Reserve's monetary policy was to a certain extent affected by the government's economic goals. For example, in order to deal with economic recovery and inflationary pressures, the Federal Reserve has carried out a series of interest rate hikes. The purpose of raising interest rates is to curb inflation and prevent the economy from overheating. However, this policy also brings many chain reactions. Interest rate hikes cause the U.S. dollar to flow back to the U.S., putting pressure on emerging markets for capital outflows, and at the same time increasing the financing costs of U.S. businesses. Moreover, the direction of US dollar monetary policy is also closely related to the global economic and political situation. For example, when international geopolitical tensions or global economic instability occur, the safe-haven property of the US dollar is highlighted, which will also affect its supply and demand relationship and value in the international currency market.

2.3. Status of US debt

The Biden administration's fiscal spending plans have led to a continuous climb in the scale of the U.S. debt. In order to implement large-scale economic stimulus plans such as the \$1.9 trillion relief bill and the \$3.5 trillion budget resolution, the government needs a lot of money, and debt issuance has become the main method of financing. The broadening of the U.S. debt scale has raised market concerns about the sustainability of U.S. debt. When global investors' confidence in U.S. debt declines, U.S. debt interest rates may rise, which will further increase the debt burden of the U.S. government. For example, in the case of countries around the world selling U.S. debt one after another, the United States has to face higher debt financing costs. In addition, the U.S. debt ceiling issue has also become the focus of political games. The Biden administration attempts to raise the debt ceiling to meet fiscal spending needs, but is opposed by the Republican Party and other parties. This kind of political dispute makes the U.S. debt issue more complex and thorny.

2.4. Inflation situation

During the Biden administration, inflation in the United States became a prominent economic problem. Large-scale fiscal stimulus plans, such as rescue plans and infrastructure expenditures during the epidemic, have led to a significant increase in the money supply. At the same time, factors such as supply chain disruptions and energy price fluctuations have also exacerbated inflationary pressures. To control inflation, the government has taken some measures, such as tightening monetary policy. However, the effect of inflation control is not ideal. The continuous rise in prices erodes consumers' purchasing power and also pose challenges to enterprises' cost control and profit margins. For example, inflation has led to an increase in raw material prices, and enterprises have to raise product prices, which in turn affects market demand and economic vitality.

2.5. Employment situation

The Biden administration has made employment as one of the important policy goals. Under the promotion of certain policies, there have been certain changes in the job market. For example, policies such as infrastructure plans and manufacturing investment have created employment opportunities for related industries. However, the recovery of the job market also faces many difficulties. On the one hand, there is a problem of mismatch between supply and demand in the labour market. Some industries face labor shortages, while others have insufficient employment opportunities. On the other hand, the transformation of the economic structure and technological progress continuously increase the skill requirements of employed people, and some traditional employment positions are impacted. Moreover, the stability of employment growth is also affected by economic cycles and policy uncertainties.

2.6. Economic policies towards China

The Biden administration has continued and strengthened its economic containment policies toward China. In terms of trade, not only have some tariff barriers from the Trump era been retained, but tariffs on Chinese products exported to the United States have also continued to be imposed. In the investment field, an executive order has been signed to limit the investment of American enterprises in Chinese entities in key high-tech fields, trying to hinder China's development in fields such as semiconductors, quantum technology, and artificial intelligence. Behind this policy is the United States' worry and competitive mentality about China's economic rise. From an economic perspective, these policies have damaged the normal economic and trade cooperation relationship between China and the United States and have had a negative impact on enterprises and consumers in both countries. For example, the expansion of American enterprises in the Chinese market is restricted, and at the same time, Chinese export enterprises also face problems such as reduced orders.

2.7. Economic policies towards Europe

The Biden administration's economic policies toward Europe are relatively complex. On the one hand, it attempts to repair relations with European allies and strengthen economic and political ties with Europe by returning to international organizations and multilateral cooperation and suspending the imposition of tariffs on some products on each other. On the other hand, some domestic policies of the United States have also triggered economic frictions with Europe. For example, the subsidy policies in the Inflation Reduction Act have aroused dissatisfaction among European countries, who are worried that it will damage the competitiveness of European enterprises in new energy and other fields. In addition, on energy issues, there are also differences in the interests and policy priorities of the United States and Europe. For example, in the process of European energy transformation, issues such as natural gas supply. U.S. policies have had an impact on Europe to a certain extent.

3. The quality of the U.S. national economy is highly correlated with the behavior of political parties and politicians.

3.1. Party concepts and economic policies

There are significant differences in economic concepts between the Democratic Party and the Republican Party in the United States. The Democratic Party tends to adopt active fiscal policies and government intervention to promote social fairness and economic growth. For example, the Biden-led Democratic government focuses on supporting the middle class and the revitalization of manufacturing and achieving these goals through large-scale fiscal spending plans. The Republican Party places more emphasis on the free market economy, advocates reducing government regulation and taxes, and encourages enterprises to develop independently. Differences in economic policies during periods of different parties in power have led to different paths of economic development in the United States. For example, in terms of tax policy, the Democratic Party may promote tax increases on high-income groups and enterprises to raise funds for social welfare and public projects, while the Republican Party tends to cut taxes to stimulate economic vitality.

3.2. Politicians' decisions and economic trends

Politicians play a key role in economic decision-making process. Their political positions, campaign promises, and the influence of interest groups will all influence the formulation and implementation of economic policies. Taking Biden as an example, he proposed a series of economic policy propositions during the election campaign, such as strengthening health care and infrastructure investment. These propositions have become an important part of economic policy since he took office. Moreover, in order to win the support of voters and deal with domestic political pressure, politicians may adopt some short-term economic policies that cater to the interests of certain groups. For example, in an election year, the government may launch some employment stimulus plans or preferential tax policies to increase voters' support rate for the ruling party.

4. American politicians and political parties shape the systems of the United States, and there are great differences in the systems of government of different parties.

4.1. Party leadership in system formulation

The economic and political systems of the United States are established and evolved under the leadership of political parties. Political parties play a key role in it, from the tax system to the financial regulatory system. For example, in the tax system reform, the Democratic Party and the Republican Party have intense debates and games around issues such as tax rates, tax structures, and tax uses. The Democratic Party often advocates that the tax system should pay more attention to fairness and ensure the source of funds for social welfare and public services by levying higher taxes on high-income earners and enterprises. The Republican Party emphasizes the impact of the tax system on economic efficiency and tends to lower tax rates to encourage corporate investment and economic growth.

4.2. The impact of institutional differences on the economy

Institutional differences under governments of different parties have a profound impact on the U.S. economy. In terms of financial supervision, when the Democratic Party is in power, it can strengthen financial supervision to prevent financial risks, such as the financial regulatory reform promoted by the Democratic Party after the 2008

financial crisis. The Republican Party may be more inclined to relax financial supervision to promote financial innovation and the activity of financial markets. This institutional difference leads to different development trends in the U.S. economy at different periods. For example, in a period of loose financial supervision, the financial market may be more active, but financial risks may also accumulate; while in a period of strict financial supervision, the stability of the financial market is enhanced, but financial innovation may be inhibited to a certain extent. It can be seen that in the financial market, the economy of political behavior and the economy of political party behavior are at the highest level of the institutional economy, and the latter is subject to the former.

5. The institutional economy of the United States is the product of politician behavior economy, political party behavior economy and government behavioral economy.

5.1. The connection between institutional economy and political parties and politicians' behaviors

The economic system of the United States is formed in the long-term interaction and decision-making process of political parties and politicians. Politicians will promote the establishment and reform of institutions in order to achieve their political goals and the demands of the interest groups they represent. Political parties integrate the behaviors of these individual politicians to form institutional propositions with party characteristics. For example, in terms of the health care system, the Democratic Party's promotion of establishing a broader healthcare coverage system is based on its concept of social fairness and ensuring people's health. At the same time, it must also win the support of middle- and low-income groups and interest groups in the healthcare industry. The Republican Party's health care reform proposals focus more on reducing the government financial burden and reducing regulations on enterprises.

5.2. Limitations of studying institutional economics without considering political parties and politicians' behaviour

If political parties and politicians' behaviors are not considered, it is impossible to fully understand the formation and operation of the institutional economy of the United States. Institutional economy is the result of the interaction between politics and the economy. Analyzing the efficiency and impact of institutions only from a purely economic perspective will ignore the key role of political factors. For example, the introduction of US trade protectionist policies cannot be explained solely from the perspective of economic interests. Political factors such as political parties maintaining the support of domestic industrial interest groups and politicians striving for the votes of specific voter groups also need to be considered.

6. Essentially, politician behavior economics, political party behavior economics and government behavioral economics are the parents of institutional economics.

6.1. Politician and political party behavior as the origin of institutional economics

In the early stages of the formation of a country's institutions, politicians formulated a series of basic economic and political systems in order to establish and consolidate political power. These initial systems laid the foundation for the

subsequent evolution of institutions. With the emergence and development of political parties, competition between political parties has promoted the continuous adjustment and improvement of institutions.

For example, in the early days of the founding of the United States, the debates and decisions of politicians on the country's economic development model, such as trade policies and fiscal policies, shaped early economic institutions. The subsequent games played by political parties around these basic institutions further promoted the refinement and evolution of institutions and provided rich material for the emergence of institutional economics.

6.2. The deepening of the economic impact of politicians, government and political parties' behavior by institutional economics

When institutional economics studies the impact of institutions on the economy, it is necessary to trace back to the origin of institutions, that is, the behavior of politicians, government and political parties. By analyzing how institutions affect the behavior of economic entities and economic performance, we can infer the economic consequences of politicians, government and political parties' behavior.

For example, studying the impact of the tax system on enterprise investment and economic growth can reveal the economic considerations of political parties when formulating tax policies. The development of institutional economics is inseparable from an in-depth understanding of politician behavior economics, political party behavior economics and government behavioral economics, and there is a close logical relationship between them. It should be pointed out that the government is made up of different political parties. There are similarities as well as many differences in political views among different parties. In general, the institutional economy is bound to be closely related to political behavior economy as well.

7. The value of establishing new disciplines of political party behavior economics, politician or statesman behavior economics, political behavior economics and government behavioral economics for analyzing and studying the rise and fall of national and world economies

7.1. Value for analyzing the rise and fall of a country's economy

7.1.1. In-depth understanding of the roots of economic policies

By studying political party behavior economics, politician or statesman behavior economics, political behavior economics and government behavioral economics, we can gain an in-depth understanding of the background for formulating national economic policies. For example, by analyzing the economic policies of different political parties in the United States at different times, we can understand how policies are influenced by political party ideologies, interest groups, and election pressures. This understanding helps predict policy change trends and assess the long-term and short-term impacts of policies on economic growth, employment, inflation, and other aspects, thus better grasping the dynamics of a country's economic rise and fall.

Based on the above considerations, over the past four years I have put forward proposals to establish four new disciplines for the first time in the world, and for the first time I have given each of these disciplines a clear definition as well.

7.1.2. Revealing political factors in economic development

Economic development depends not only on economic factors but also on political factors, which are equally crucial. The new discipline can reveal how political decision-making processes and the distribution of political power affect the allocation of economic resources and economic development paths. Taking the United States as an example, policy deadlocks caused by political polarization can hamper economic reform and development. By studying the behaviors of political parties and politicians, we can clearly see the role of these political factors in economic rise and fall.

7.1.3. Optimizing the design of the economic system

Understanding the impact of political parties and politicians' behaviors on the economic system can provide a basis for reforming and optimizing the economic system. By analyzing the operating effects of the existing system under the influence of political parties and politicians' behaviors, we can discover the defects and shortcomings of the system and propose more reasonable system design plans to promote long-term stable economic development and avoid economic recession caused by unreasonable systems.

7.2. Value for analyzing the rise and fall of the world economy

7.2.1. Interpreting political motives in international economic relations

In the context of globalization, the economic policies of various countries interact with each other. Studying political party behavior economics and politician or statesman behavior economics can help interpret the political motives of various countries in international economic relations. For example, behind the economic policies of the United States towards China and Europe are complex political party and politician factors. Understanding these factors can better deal with international economic frictions, maintain the stability of the international economic order, and avoid global economic fluctuations caused by political factors.

7.2.2. Predicting the trend of global economic policies

The behaviour of political parties and politicians in different countries affects the direction of global economic policies. By studying the economics of political party behavior and politician behavior economics of various countries, we can establish models to predict changing trends of global economic policies, such as trade policies and monetary policies. It is of great significance for enterprises to make international investment and trade decisions and for international organizations to formulate coordinated policies, and helps to deal with the uncertainties of the global economic rise and fall.

7.2.3. Promoting international economic cooperation and coordination

Understanding the characteristics and motives of political parties and politicians in various countries can provide better strategies for international economic cooperation and coordination. By finding the common economic interests of political parties and politicians in various countries, we can resolve international economic conflicts, promote multilateral and bilateral economic cooperation, and promote the common prosperity of the global economy, and avoid global economic division and recession caused by the behavior of politics, politicians and political parties in individual countries.

7.3. Research on the top level of institutional economics also needs to be based on the reclassification of human social systems.

Currently, there are only six types of human social systems. This classification method has led politicians to have a vague understanding of social systems. The naming of the socialist system is inaccurate and its definition ambiguous, which has led to chaos in social governance in some countries. The current classification model of social systems actually pits capitalist society against socialist society, causing conflicts, confrontations and wars in the global ideological realm. However, in reality, the social systems of the United States and Israel have many similarities with that of China. Israel even has many kibbutz communities that are similar to the labor and distribution systems under the communist system. Apparently, the current classification method of human social systems does not conform to reality. Therefore, from the perspective of history and philosophy, I have further creatively improved on the current six types of human social systems in another article and subdivided human social systems according to whether a society or a country possesses morality, conscience and empathy. In this way, in this colorful world, basically every country can quickly identify its own social system. This is the first time in the world that human social systems have been turned into something like an encyclopedia, with a wide variety of categories.

This helps to free human social systems from ambiguous and simplistic classifications and from systems of "democracy" and "freedom" that easily confuse the public, so that ordinary people can relatively clearly recognize the political positions of political parties and politicians in different countries as well as the political systems they have formulated, without being bewildered by the names of political parties or countries. It is also hoped that this will be conducive to revealing the evil nature of countries that commit large-scale crimes, severely cracking down on such crimes, preventing the United Nations from becoming a protective umbrella for these evil and criminal countries, quickly and effectively disintegrating and restructuring the evil countries established by such evil political groups, achieving the rapid cutting off of the channels through which evil political groups in regions plunder huge amounts of illegal economic incomes, eliminating the malignant tumors of the world, facilitating the effective governance of the world, maintaining the normal world order, promoting the healthy development of the economy and truly realizing the sustainable peace of the world.

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